

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PREALBUMIN AS A MALNUTRITION INDICATOR IN ELDERLY PATIENTS
ADMITTED TO A SKILLED NURSING FACILITY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

Malnutrition is underdiagnosed in the geriatric population residing in a skilled nursing facility (SNF) and is associated with increased morbidity, hospital readmissions, and multiple complications. Although several screening tools have been developed, malnutrition still is inadequately recognized and managed. A prealbumin level is a potentially useful malnutrition marker and can be used to determine the need for nutritional supplements. This project examined the prevalence of malnutrition and the efficacy of an oral enriched protein supplement in a population of patients in the SNF setting. A retrospective program evaluation of existing data was completed to evaluate the efficacy of an existing treatment plan for those at risk for malnutrition. Existing patient data from four SNFs were screened for eligibility criteria: Data included demographic information, admission prealbumin levels, protocol-based protein supplement received, and a 30-day prealbumin level. Eighty patients were included in the study. Seventy-six percent of the patients had malnutrition (prealbumin <17mg/dl). The median age was 82.6 years, 45% were male. Prealbumin scores of patients at baseline (M = 10.54, SD = 3.52) increased from 30-day follow-up (M = 15.05, SD = 6.36). There was a statistically significant interaction effect for protocol (F (1, 37) = 35.99, p < .001); change in prealbumin scores was dependent on protocol. The protein supplement group (protocol group) had an increase in prealbumin scores from baseline (M = 9.79, SD = 3.23) to 30-day (M = 17.03). Statistical significance was found in an interaction effect for protocol (F (1, 37) = 35.99, p < .001); change in prealbumin scores

was dependent on protocol. Despite higher initial average prealbumin scores at baseline (non-protocol group), not receiving the oral protein supplements as prescribed, experienced decreases in their prealbumin scores from baseline ($M = 12.70$, $SD = 3.56$) to 30-day follow-up ($M = 9.30$, $SD = 15.05$). A prealbumin level upon admission at a SNF is a reliable tool to evaluate malnutrition. The use of an oral protein supplement should be considered for patients with existing malnutrition in the SNF, which could prevent further malnutrition and adverse complications.

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BACKGROUND

Needs Assessment/Problem Statement

Malnutrition in skilled nursing facilities is a common occurrence in the geriatric population, affecting approximately 60-80% of the residents in these homes (Cereda et al., 2011). However, malnutrition continues to remain unnoticed and undertreated, causing a variety of unfavorable outcomes at a colossal cost to the individual patients as well as the health care system. Malnutrition prolongs recovery from illness, increases complications, and expends more resources (Cawood, Elia, & Stratton, 2011).

Malnutrition has been defined as a “state of nutrition in which a deficiency, excess or imbalance of energy, protein, and other nutrients causes measurable adverse effects on tissue/body form (body shape, size, and composition) function, and clinical outcome” (Freijer et al., 2012, p. 136). Changes in the body’s metabolism occur that increase daily nutritional needs and subsequently deplete protein from the body. This adversely impacts every organ system in the body, resulting in life-threatening consequences on a physiological level and contributing to increased morbidity and mortality (Freijer et al., 2012). Malnutrition has been associated with undesirable outcomes such as increased length of stay in skilled nursing facilities, readmissions to the hospital, pressure sores, delirium, and complications from infections (Vischer et al., 2011).

Insufficient oral intake compounded by additional nutritional requirements during an active disease state may exacerbate underlying chronic disease and lead to poor absorption and excessive nutrient loss (Gout, Barker, & Crowe, 2009). This poor dietary intake may be a consequence of an acute or chronic disease state (Lopez-Contreras,

Torralba, Zamora, & Perez-Llamas, 2012). Poor dietary intake leads to a malnutrition state, which may lead to increased morbidity and mortality and increased complications. The influence of malnutrition on the elderly's health status, and their increased need for care, creates a tremendous burden on illness in western societies, generating billions of dollars annually due to costs of these complications (Meijers, Halfens, Wilson, & Schols, 2012). The most appropriate method to screen for malnutrition for this group of patients has not been recognized clearly (Lopez-Contreras et al., 2012)

Currently, there are six nutritional screening tools used in nursing homes to predict malnutrition in the elderly. Some screening tools are based on biochemical and clinical indices, other tools use anthropometry, mobility, cognitive state, and self-perception of health and nutritional status, and still other screening forms use a combination of medical history and clinical and subjective data (Meijers et al., 2011; Poulia et al., 2011). According to the literature, malnutrition exists at every stage of admission to a nursing home using any one or a combination of these screening tools. However, most studies recognize that the screening tools are labor intensive, dependent on the patient or family member's memory, and subject to personnel bias (Cereda et al., 2011; Meijers et al., 2011; Poulia et al., 2011; Vischer et al., 2011). Results may be difficult to compare across studies given the wide assortment of laboratory and anthropometric parameters that most nutritional screening tools use, with different measurement levels, values, and defined nutritional status. Furthermore, the screening process and tools may vary greatly with assessing malnutrition and could give false positive or false negative results.

The most critical time period to screen and implement treatment for the geriatric population admitted to a skilled nursing facility is within the first 24-48 hours of admission (Drescher et al., 2010; Vischer et al., 2011). Traditionally, the marker used for malnutrition has been the serum albumin level. However, serum albumin is not an adequate indicator for malnutrition due to its long half-life (14-20 days) and the effect of external factors such as hydration, posture, and hepatic and renal impairment. The serum prealbumin has a shorter half-life (2-3 days) and is thought to be an accurate indicator of malnutrition (Drescher et al., 2010). Studies that used nutritional screening tools along with a serum prealbumin predicted malnutrition more accurately in the geriatric nursing home population (Drescher et al., 2010; Manders et al., 2009).

In the nursing home setting, the geriatric population's weight loss and malnutrition are predominantly triggered by a decline in food intake. Nursing home elderly often have a low intake of energy and micronutrients, which leads to malnutrition and decreased serum protein. The development of malnutrition could be prevented by an improvement of dietary intake, such as implementing the use of an oral enriched nutritional supplement (Manders et al., 2009). Studies have shown that oral nutritional supplementation has improved the nutritional status of institutionalized elderly with fewer complications and deaths, as well as reduced length of hospital stay (Christensson, Ek, & Unosson, 2001). Therefore, oral nutritional supplements may be used as an adjuvant to a normal diet to facilitate the prevention of malnutrition. Studies conducted on nursing home geriatric populations identify malnutrition as a problem (Cereda et al., 2011; Drescher et al., 2010; Lopez-Contreras et al., 2012; Poulia et al., 2011; Vischer et

al., 2012). However, there is very little information on the use of oral enriched nutritional supplements to prevent or treat malnutrition.

Eliminating the cumbersome nutritional screening tools and drawing a serum prealbumin level within the first 24-48 hours of admission to a skilled nursing facility, followed by subsequent implementation of a standardized oral enriched protein supplement, may reduce malnutrition in the geriatric nursing home population. The purpose of this project was to evaluate the efficacy of an oral enriched protein supplement program on prealbumin levels in an elderly population within long-term care facilities.

Supporting Framework: Awareness-to-Adherence Model

Geriatric nursing home residents are at high risk for malnutrition. Of those recently transferred from the acute hospital to skilled nursing facilities, 28-42% were malnourished upon admission. Malnutrition has significant consequences for the geriatric population, healthcare services, and society as a whole, including increased risk for morbidity, readmissions to the hospital, prolonged discharge, and dependence on outside health care needs (Rasheed & Woods, 2012). However, these risk factors can be diminished if malnutrition is recognized early and treated effectively. For this purpose, a borrowed theory such as the Awareness-to-Adherence Model in the skilled nursing facilities for malnutrition could be used for this project.

The Awareness-to-Adherence Model (see Figure 1) suggested by Pathman, Konrad, Freud, Freeman, and Koch (1996) is a model for physician compliance describing four stages from evidence to adherence. This model can be expanded and applied to additional clinical practice roles such as the DNP prepared nurse practitioner.

Pathman et al. recommended that when clinicians accomplish their goals with evidence-based practice, they must first become aware of the guidelines or the evidence-based practice changes (*awareness*), agree with it in principle (*agreement*), then determine whether it is appropriate and reasonable to adopt into their own practice (*adoption*), and lastly follow these at appropriate times (*adherence*). The Awareness-to-Adherence Model was initiated for physicians to comprehend and follow practice guidelines for pediatric vaccinations for hepatitis B.

Figure 1. The Awareness-to-Adherence Model.

Applying the Awareness-to-Adherence Model to this project starts with the evidence that malnutrition in the geriatric nursing home patient is underdiagnosed and untreated, since the majority of this population, the clinicians, caregivers, and nursing home staff are unaware of the patients' nutritional needs. In this case, the clinician needs to become aware of the severity of malnutrition upon admission to the skilled nursing facility (*awareness*), then agree with this knowledge and severity of the condition

(*agreement*), then determine whether it is appropriate and feasible to use the oral enriched protein supplement for this patient (*adoption*), and finally accomplish nutritional compliance at the appropriate times (*adherence*). In addition, the Awareness-to-Adherence Model can be utilized by the patients and their families to assist in their nutritional compliance to decrease the negative effects of malnutrition. The same principle can also be applied to nursing home staff and dieticians concerning the early diagnosis and treatment of malnutrition. The nursing home staff and dieticians should be aware of the evidence-based practice guidelines of drawing a prealbumin level on newly admitted patients, then the personnel should agree with these guidelines. Next, the nursing home staff and dietician should determine whether these practice guidelines work in their own practice of educating about and preventing malnutrition. Finally, these practices guidelines should be followed with every patient admitted in the skilled nursing facility regardless of age or diagnosis.

When the clinician has recommended an appropriate treatment plan for the malnutrition, the aforementioned steps may begin again for the patient and family members. For the patient to agree with the malnutrition treatment plan, he/she must be aware of the options for treatment or when suitable the complications of malnutrition, accept the treatment and management of the malnutrition recommended is appropriate, and be able to comply with the treatment plan. This should involve an integration of the patient's values and beliefs, which will need to be explored for adequate compliance.

Applying the model will help ensure that all interventions are aimed at enhancing the overall nutritional capacity of the geriatric nursing home population. This will potentially result in better patient outcomes, including decreased morbidity and mortality,

decreased complications from urinary tract infections and/or pneumonia, and improved quality of life. Newly admitted geriatric nursing patients would gain improvement in quality of life and length of nursing home stay would be reduced, along with readmission rates to the hospital, ultimately decreasing healthcare costs.

Project Goals/Objectives

This project utilized a retrospective design and program evaluation to evaluate the efficacy of an existing treatment plan for patients in a skilled nursing facility that suffer from or are at risk for malnutrition. In accordance with existing practice, prealbumin levels were obtained from the newly admitted nursing home elderly population. Based on the degree of malnutrition, the newly admitted nursing home patient was then prescribed an oral enriched protein supplement. A prealbumin level was again reevaluated 30 days later for comparison.

The measureable outcomes for this project included the following:

1. Evaluate the efficacy of the oral protein supplement protocol on the admission prealbumin levels as compared to the 30-day reevaluation of the prealbumin levels.
2. Evaluate the difference between those skilled nursing facility patients receiving the oral protein supplement protocol as prescribed (protocol group), to those not receiving the oral protein supplement as prescribed (non-protocol group).
3. Determine if high-risk patients (those with dementia and Parkinson's Disease) have a significantly lower admission prealbumin level and 30-day prealbumin level than patients who are not high-risk.

4. Determine the need for a protocol change in the skilled nursing facilities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Data collected for the review of literature were selected from databases such as PubMed and CINAHL. Keywords such as elderly, nursing homes, prealbumin, malnutrition, quality of life, costs of malnutrition, oral supplements were used in individual searches as well as a combined word or term searches. The researcher considered journal articles and literature written in English that included the aforementioned words in the abstract or in the title of the article and were published within the last 5 years. Data were evaluated to identify causes, consequences, treatment, and management of malnutrition and the elderly nursing home population. Additional information was sought regarding screening tools, protein supplementation, and cost effect of malnutrition. This review of literature will present topics in following areas: (a) malnutrition and quality of life in the elderly, (b) economic costs associated with malnutrition, (c) assessment and screening tools used for malnutrition, and (d) the use of oral supplements in the malnourished elderly.

Malnutrition and Quality of Life in the Elderly

Rasheed and Woods (2013) conducted a systematic review to assess the effects of malnutrition on quality of life, finding that participants diagnosed with malnutrition were more likely to experience poor quality of life. A common theme found in the reviewed studies was that interventions designed to improve nutritional status significantly enhanced quality of life both in physical and mental aspects. However, a limitation found in reviewing the studies was the lack of a universally accepted *gold standard* for evaluating nutritional status. Having an accepted universal nutritional assessment

validation tool to categorize patients into varying degrees of nutritional status will facilitate the comparison of study results across different study populations.

A study by Crogan and Pasvogel (2003) found that more than 75% of the nursing home elderly suffered from malnutrition. This study primarily looked at body mass index (BMI) to diagnose malnutrition. The researchers recognized the influence of malnutrition on quality of life. Residents with a BMI less than 22 indicated illness or malnutrition as per the Nutrition Screening Initiative guidelines. A significant correlation was found between BMI and functional status such as eating, personal hygiene, and toilet use. Depression was not a significant indicator of low BMI or malnutrition in this population. In conclusion, a low BMI indicating malnutrition was found to influence quality of life negatively.

Economic Costs Associated with Malnutrition

Malnutrition has been identified as a leading cause of increased mortality, increased length of stay, more general practitioner visits, more intensive nursing care, increased requirement of nursing home care, decreased quality of life, and increased complication rates in the European elderly nursing home population (Freijer et al., 2012; Meijers et al., 2011). Evaluation of the research demonstrated increased costs associated with the effects of malnutrition on the elderly nursing home population.

Meijers et al. (2011) determined the economic implications of malnutrition in nursing homes particularly by evaluating use of resources and time spent on nutritional screening, monitoring, and treatment of malnutrition. Normal nutritional care in the nursing home averaged about \$426 million per year, and the total extra cost for managing malnutrition was estimated at an additional \$373 million per year. Therefore, Meijers et

al. indicated that the cost of managing nursing home patients at risk of malnutrition is approximately \$2,676 less per patient than managing malnourished patients. According to the researchers, preventing patients from becoming malnourished would be cost effective.

Freijer et al. (2012) considered the additional costs of disease related malnutrition in the European healthcare sector including hospitals, nursing and residential homes, and home care settings. The management of patients with disease related malnutrition estimated an additional cost of \$1.9 billion in 2011. This additional cost equals 2.1% of the national health care expenditure for the Netherlands and 4.9% of the total costs for the healthcare sector in Europe. The researchers concluded that disease related malnutrition was significant. Early recognition and treatment of disease related malnutrition could reduce length of stay.

Assessment and Screening Tools Used For Malnutrition

The current literature addresses malnutrition as a common problem in the elderly population newly admitted to nursing homes. Several nutritional screening tools are available to evaluate this risk of malnutrition. The researchers evaluated a variety of nutritional screening tools developed to help identify malnutrition in the elderly nursing home population (Cereda et al., 2011, Cereda, Valzolgher, & Pedrolli, 2008; Drescher et al., 2010; Neyens et al., 2012; Poulia et al., 2011; Verbrugge et al., 2012; Vischer et al., 2011). Some of these nutritional screening tools are based on biochemical and clinical indexes such as the Nutritional Risk Index and the Geriatric Nutritional Risk Index. Others focus on anthropometry, mobility, cognitive state, and self-perception of health and nutrition (e.g., the Mini Nutritional Assessment and the shorter version known as the

Mini Nutritional Assessment Screening Tool Form, and the Malnutrition Universal Screening Tool). Others combined the data from medical history and clinical and subjective evaluation of the patient, such as the Subjective Global Assessment, and the Nutritional Risk Screening 2002 (Poulia et al., 2011). However, the various nutritional screening tools that were found throughout the literature varied in the degree of assessment and evaluation of malnutrition, either by overestimating the nutritional risk or underestimating the nutritional risk factors in the elderly population. Early recognition of malnutrition, especially upon admission, and implementation of a plan was key; however, the measure used to identify malnutrition varied significantly across all the research literature reviewed (Cereda et al., 2008, 2011; Drescher et al., 2010; Neyens et al., 2012; Poulia et al., 2011; Verbrugge et al., 2012; Vischer et al., 2011). Clinical review of research indicated that malnutrition leads to negative effects on a patient's prognosis and can result in multiple complications including prolonged hospital stay, increased morbidity and mortality, and subsequent increase in healthcare costs (Cereda et al., 2011; Poulia et al., 2011).

In another study, Potter and Luxton (1999) examined the effectiveness of prealbumin levels as a routine diagnostic tool for assessing malnutrition. The study evaluated the effect of malnutrition on emergency department admissions, comparing albumin and prealbumin levels as nutritional markers on hospitalized patients. Potter and Luxton explored whether nutritional supplementation was implemented for those patients categorized as malnourished, as well as evaluating the length of stay and mortality rates for those considered malnourished. The researchers also conducted a cost analysis of using a prealbumin level upon admission as a screening tool for malnutrition. The

clinical review concluded that when screening for malnutrition, albumin was inadequate and half of the patients were actually malnourished. Prealbumin was a more suitable and accurate method for screening of malnutrition. Patients with malnutrition were noted to have a significantly higher mortality rates and almost doubled the length of hospital stay compared to those with adequate nutritional status. The cost analysis demonstrated a significant savings by using prealbumin levels as a measurement tool for malnutrition. In conclusion, malnutrition was underdiagnosed and associated with longer length of stay and increased mortality rate.

A similar study by Devoto et al. (2006) assessed malnutrition as a common occurrence among hospitalized patients. It was associated with a poor prognosis and increased mortality. A prealbumin level can be a useful screening tool for identifying malnutrition in those at nutritional risk. A prealbumin level was drawn on newly admitted hospitalized patients during a 3-month period of time and the Detailed Nutritional Assessment (DNA) screening tool was used as a reference to determine malnutrition. The Subjective Global Assessment (SGA) and the Prognostic Inflammatory and Nutritional Index (PINI) score were also compared to evaluate the effectiveness of the prealbumin level on diagnosing malnutrition. Results of prealbumin levels indicated adequate concordance index at 76.8% with the standard DNA screening tool and reliable sensitivity/specificity profile of 83.1%/76.7% when compared with the SGA and PINI. In conclusion, a prealbumin level is a sufficient and reliable screening tool in the evaluation of malnutrition.

The Use of Oral Supplements in the Malnourished Elderly

Arnaud-Battandier et al. (2004) and Manders et al. (2009) evaluated the effect of nutritional supplementation on nursing home residents' nutritional status and morbidity, and associated costs of complications from malnutrition. The clinical review explored the beneficial effects of oral protein supplementations on those diagnosed with malnutrition. Appropriate use of an oral protein supplement effectively reduced the level of malnutrition among the elderly population, and even counteracted the development of malnutrition in this group. In addition, the researchers determined that the use of oral protein supplementation may contribute to a reduction of associated health care costs.

A systematic review by Cawood et al. (2012) reviewed disease related malnutrition and the efficacy of a high protein oral nutritional supplement in offsetting the effects of malnutrition. The researchers reviewed 36 randomized controlled trials ranging across healthcare settings and patient diagnoses, along with different use of oral protein supplementation. A significant reduction in a range of complications such as adequate wound healing, pressure ulcers, and infection rates occurred in both the hospital and community settings. Other findings included reduced readmission rates to the hospital and improvement in weight. The systematic review concluded that oral protein supplements produce beneficial clinical outcomes, along with reduced economic implications.

Neelemaat et al. (2012) and Myint et al. (2012) evaluated the effects of short-term oral nutritional supplements on fall risk and fractures. A significant difference in BMI, total protein, and intake of energy was noted in the interventional oral nutritional supplement group as opposed to the control group. The length of stay was shortened by

almost 4 days, along with the total number of infection episodes, and the risk of falling decreased by almost 50%. A significantly reduced number of poor outcomes, length of stay, and complications was found in malnourished elderly patients receiving an oral nutritional supplement.

In summary, patients were underdiagnosed for malnutrition and a sufficient amount of literature on the use of oral protein supplementation demonstrates its potential to ameliorate the effects of malnutrition. Studies support the use of prealbumin as a marker for malnutrition and malnutrition as a predictive indicator of length of stay, morbidity, and mortality. However, few studies examined the relationship of prealbumin level directly to these outcomes as an independent predictive marker (Devoto et al., 2006; Potter & Luxton, 1999). This project aimed to close this gap by evaluating the efficacy of prealbumin level as a marker for diagnosing malnutrition and the effects of an oral protein supplement on nutritional status.

METHODS

Ethical Considerations

This retrospective program evaluation project was presented to the California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board (IRB) and approval was obtained. All patient information was protected according to IRB policies as well as policies surrounding the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPPA; U.S. Department of Health & Human Services, n.d.).

Project Implementation

Existing data were obtained from an independent primary care group; data spanned the time frame from October 1, 2012 to October 1, 2013. The data were obtained from electronic medical records (EMRs). Data included patient demographic information (age, gender, ethnicity), height, weight, BMI, skilled nursing facility name, admitting diagnosis, length of stay, primary cause of hospital admission, and comorbidities. Additional information was collected, including oral protein supplement dosage and a prealbumin level obtained within 24-48 hours after admission to a skilled nursing facility for all elderly patients regardless of age or diagnosis as part of baseline laboratory values already established for patients being admitted. Follow-up prealbumin lab values drawn 30 days after admission to the skilled nursing facility according to the protocol were also recorded.

Samples in the database were previously analyzed through the local laboratory at each nursing home. The normal range for prealbumin level is 17-35 mg/dl, according to the assay manufacturers. A prealbumin level was obtained within the first 24-48 hours of admission to the skilled nursing facility on the elderly patient. The treatment protocol

reviewed was based on the degree of malnutrition and implementation of an oral enriched protein supplement called Prostat 64, which is used at all the skilled nursing home facilities. Prostat 64 is a high calorie complete protein liquid, with added Arginine, Citrulline, Cystine, Zinc, and Vitamin C (see Table 1 for more nutrient information). Prostat contains “17 grams of hydrolyzed complete protein to reduce protein energy/calorie malnutrition, build muscle, repair tissue, fight infections, and reduce overall morbidity/mortality” (“Pro-Stat Sugar Free AWC,” n.d., para. 3). Prostat is supplied at the skilled nursing facilities as a house stock supply. It comes in an 887ml bottle; each patient is given 30ml orally as a medication pass prescribed by the physician.

Table 1

Composition of the Dietary Supplement Per Serving

Component	Amount
Nutrient	30 ml
Calories	101
Calories from Fat	0
Total carbohydrates (g)	10.2
Sugar (g)	10.2
Protein (g)	15
Sodium (mg)	15
Potassium (mg)	16
Phosphorus (mg)	6

The treatment protocol for malnutrition with implementation of Prostat 64 was as follows:

- Prealbumin level between 15-17mg/dl, Prostat 64 30ml BID
- Prealbumin level between 11-14mg/dl, Prostat 64 30ml TID
- Prealbumin level < 10mg/dl, Prostat 64 30ml QID

The prealbumin level was measured 30 days after the initial screening and implementation of the oral enriched protein supplement protocol. Patients who met the criteria for malnutrition and did not receive the protein supplement as prescribed were categorized into a non-protocol group. Not all of the skilled nursing facility patients received the malnutrition protocol due to variations in staff implementation, either due to a prealbumin level not being obtained within the first 24-48 hours of admission or because the enriched oral protein supplementation was not given as prescribed.

Sequence of Activities

A retrospective design was chosen for this program evaluation project. A total of four skilled nursing facilities were chosen for the evaluation of the prealbumin level drawn 24-28 hours after admission to the skilled nursing facility. Evaluation of the treatment protocol guidelines, which consisted of the oral enriched protein supplementation, was prescribed within 4-8 hours after the initial prealbumin level results. A prealbumin level was again drawn 30 days from the first level and reevaluated for comparison.

Organizational Setting

The project was reviewed and analyzed in four skilled nursing facilities in Torrance, California, under the care of one internal medicine primary care physician and five mid-level providers. The chosen primary care practice selected for the review and analysis of this practice protocol project was chosen given the ease of access, locale, overall availability, and potential benefits for the providers in the practice, which will also benefit the elderly patients.

The selected skilled nursing facilities are freestanding and Medicare/MediCal approved with bed capacity from 80-99. Full occupancy ranges from 80-95%. These facilities provide short and long term care, from rehabilitation to extensive special care needs to complex medical care for patients with reduced physical functioning. While serving a diverse population of male and female patients ranging in age from 45 to over 100 years old, with the average age being 65 to 84 years old. Demographic characteristics for the elderly population served in the skilled nursing facilities vary by age, race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic background.

The primary care provider serving this select population of elderly patients include one certified, licensed physician (MD), one nurse practitioner (masters prepared NP, currently a DNP candidate), and four physician assistants (PAs) with specialty training and credentialing in adult/geriatrics, general medicine, internal medicine, and family practice. The mid-level providers in this practice round on this elderly patient population daily Monday through Saturday, with the physician supervising as needed. All documentation of assessment and plan is completely computerized with EMR for the practice.

The skilled nursing facilities employ one registered nurse (RN) supervisor for every eight hour shift, three licensed vocational nurses (LVNs) to pass medications, one licensed vocational nurse (LVN) for treatment on duty 8 hours per 24 hours, one certified nurse's assistant (CNA) for every 10-14 patients to provide personal hygiene care per shift and a registered dietician (RD) on duty for 8 hours 2 days per week. Physicians are required by state mandates to see all new admissions within 72 hours of being admitted to

the skilled nursing facility, then every 30 days for 90 days, and then every 60 days thereafter.

Stakeholders Involved

The purpose of this protocol guideline project was to review and analyze the current malnutrition protocol being implemented on the elderly patients newly admitted to the skilled nursing facility among a primary care practice employing one physician, one NP, and four PAs. Effectively engaging these individuals as key stakeholders was vital for the success of this project. The key stakeholders for the project were the primary care provider and mid-level providers caring for the skilled nursing facility patients, the nursing staff, the RDs, director of nursing, administration, as well as the elderly patients who receive the malnutrition screening and oral protein supplementation. Other stakeholders include hospitals, Medicare, MediCal, and any other secondary insurance providers. Prior to program implementation, a formal letter of agreement was obtained as evidence of support from the practice management personnel.

Patient Participation/Selection

The target population at the four skilled nursing facilities was all newly admitted patients regardless of age and admitting diagnosis. Patients were excluded from this project if for some reason a prealbumin level was not obtained within 24-48 hours of admission and/or either readmission to the hospital or early discharge home from the skilled nursing facility occurred, preventing a 30 day comparison prealbumin level from being drawn. Further exclusion criteria included having a normal prealbumin level upon admission to the skilled nursing facility.

Evaluation Methods

Measures for central tendency were calculated including frequencies, means, ranges, and standard deviations (SDs) to describe sample characteristics. Inferential statistics were performed to compare admission prealbumin level and the 30-day prealbumin level after implementation of the oral enriched protein supplement was administered, as well as to compare the protocol and non-protocol groups. The statistical analyses for the main outcome parameters were restricted to participants with complete follow-up. Statistical significance was defined as $p < .05$. Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS for Windows version 20.0.

RESULTS/OUTCOMES

Demographic and clinical characteristics of the sample population are summarized in Table 2. Patients meeting eligibility criteria totaled 107; however, there were missing data for 27 patients, leaving complete data for 80 patients. The median age of the sample was 82.6 years (SD = 10.32); the male (45%) to female (55%) ratio was equal between the two groups. Of the participants, 63.8% were Caucasian, and 43.8% were admitted to one skilled nursing facility. Twenty-one of the 80 patients were diagnosed as having malnutrition but were discharged prior to the 30-day reevaluation of the prealbumin level. The non-protocol group had a total of 10 patients.

Table 2

Sample Demographics

Sample Characteristics	Mean (SD)	Frequency (%)
Age	82.6 (10.3)	
Gender		
Male		36 (45%)
Female		44 (55%)
Prealbumin levels		
Admission	13.1 (5.9)	
30 day	15.2 (6.3)	
Ethnicity		
White		51 (63.8%)
Black		7 (8.8%)
Asian		16 (20%)
Hispanic		5 (6.3%)
Other		1 (1.3%)
SNF		
#1		35 (43.8%)
#2		21 (26.3%)
#3		20 (25%)
#4		4 (5%)
Length of stay in days	52.4 (59.6)	

Note. N = 80.

According to the prealbumin level upon admission to the skilled nursing facility, 18 patients had a normal nutritional state defined by a prealbumin level greater or equal than 18mg/dl, six patients were mildly malnourished defined by a prealbumin level 15-17mg/dl, 24 patients were moderately malnourished with a prealbumin level of 11-14mg/dl, and 28 patients were severely malnourished with a prealbumin level lesser or equal than 10mg/dl. Prealbumin levels between those patients receiving the oral protein supplement protocol as prescribed (protocol group), were compared to those not receiving the oral protein supplement as prescribed (non-protocol group). A repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a statistically significant effect for time ($F(1, 37) = 4.69, p = .04$), with overall prealbumin scores of patients at baseline ($M = 10.54, SD = 3.52$) increasing by 30-day follow-up ($M = 15.05, SD = 6.36$). However, the presence of a statistically significant interaction effect for protocol ($F(1, 37) = 35.99, p < .001$) revealed that the change in prealbumin scores was dependent on protocol (see Figure 2), with those receiving oral protein supplements experiencing gains in prealbumin scores from baseline ($M = 9.79, SD = 3.23$) to 30-day follow-up ($M = 17.03$). Despite higher initial average prealbumin scores at baseline, those not receiving oral protein supplements experienced decreases in their prealbumin scores from baseline ($M = 12.70, SD = 3.56$) to 30-day follow-up ($M = 9.30, SD = 15.05$).

Figure 2. *Prealbumin level by time and protocol.*

High-risk patients were compared for a lower admission prealbumin and 30-day prealbumin levels than those patients who were not high-risk. While a repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a statistically significant effect for time ($F(1, 39) = 15.69, p < .001$), with the pattern of means remaining substantively identical to those reported previously, risk status (high versus low-risk) made no significant impact on patients' recovery over 30 days (see Figure 3); $F(1, 39) = 0.03, p = .87$).

Figure 3. Prealbumin level by time and risk status.

DISCUSSION

One of the key findings of this program evaluation project in newly admitted skilled nursing facility patients was that malnutrition was highly prevalent in this population, with 76% of patients being identified as having malnutrition upon admission to the skilled nursing facility. These findings are consistent with the literature on malnutrition in the skilled nursing home population. Being malnourished or at risk for malnutrition may already exist at the time of hospitalization. It is sensible to conclude that hospitalization and the circumstances leading to that hospitalization such as disease state may accelerate the process of malnutrition (Verbrugghe et al., 2012).

There was a significant improvement between baseline prealbumin levels compared to the 30-day prealbumin levels for those patients receiving the protocol as prescribed. Previous findings related to protein supplementation consumption in institutionalized patients were shown to improve protein intake and nutritional assessment scores and reduce length of stay (Arnaud-Battandier et al., 2004; Manders et al., 2009; Neelemaat et al., 2012). However, in this project, patients who did not receive the oral protein supplement per protocol experienced decreases in 30-day prealbumin levels when compared to baseline prealbumin levels. This was not consistent with some of the literature. Manders et al. (2009) found favorable outcomes regarding nutritional status despite low compliance rates. Some reasons for low compliance included taste of the nutritional drink, the scheduled timing for taking the nutritional drink (between meals), and nursing staff not giving the drink due to time constraints. It should be noted that the non-protocol group for this project was relatively small in size, which could have yielded inaccurate results. Also, this group had overall higher baseline prealbumin levels

than the protocol group, which may indicate other factors such as admission diagnoses or potential adverse effects like urinary tract infections or pneumonia that could be addressed in future studies.

No significant association was found in baseline prealbumin levels in patients potentially at high risk for malnutrition such as those with dementia or Parkinson's disease when compared to the 30-day prealbumin levels. This finding is not consistent with some of the literature citing that dementia was a key correlate to higher risk for malnutrition. Many of these studies excluded patients that had a diagnosis of dementia due to the inability to implement the nutritional screening tool related to their mental status. Other studies identified a decrease in food intake due to lack of assistance with meals, food withdrawal while waiting for radiologic procedures, mental status, and feeding refusal for increased risks for malnutrition (Cereda et al., 2008, 2011; Devoto et al., 2006; Drescher et al., 2010; Neyens et al., 2012; Poulia et al., 2011; Verbrugge et al., 2012; Vischer et al., 2011). Many nutritional screening methods use some combination of nutrition related health questionnaires to be answered either by the patient and/or family members or in some cases by the staff at the nursing home facilities. Using a biochemical marker such as prealbumin for the diagnosis of malnutrition allows every patient to be evaluated for the risk of malnutrition regardless of underlying diagnosis or mental status.

This project had several limitations. It had a relatively small sample size for both the protocol and non-protocol group. Recommendations for future studies include reproducing this project by using a larger study sample. In working with a retrospective evaluation of existing data, the DNP candidate was limited to the data recorded.

However, this limitation did produce a non-protocol group, which allowed the DNP candidate to compare these results to those of the protocol group. In addition, many patients were discharged either home or to a lower level of care prior to the 30-day reevaluation of the prealbumin level. Therefore, many patients were lost to follow-up, which could cause an outpatient readmission back to the hospital. Another limitation was that during retrieval of the existing data, it was difficult to track and/or trend readmissions, length of stay, and/or new onset of complications such as urinary tract infections or pneumonia. Moreover, when interpreting the findings from this project, a low prealbumin level may also be affected by an inflammatory process. This study did not measure any inflammatory markers such as a C-reactive protein, which may be used to evaluate the influence of inflammation on prealbumin levels and potentially the outcome measures (Hrnciarikova et al., 2007). Lastly, in the skilled nursing facility, length of stay may have multiple influencing factors, not just malnutrition and admitting diagnosis. Patients may have stayed longer due to family issues, financial reasons, or waiting for bed availability at a lower level of care such as a board and care or assisted living facility.

Recommendations for practice would include adjusting the protocol guideline for implementing the oral enriched protein supplement once daily to those at risk for malnutrition with a prealbumin level upon admission between 18-21mg/dl. Another recommendation would be to continue using the oral enriched protein supplement once daily when on reevaluation the patient achieved a prealbumin level between 18-21mg/dl. Lastly, since many patients were discharged from the skilled nursing facility prior to the

30-day reevaluation of the prealbumin level, it is recommended to check a prealbumin level on day 14, day 30, and day 45 as patients remain at the skilled nursing facility.

Cost analysis reveals that a considerable savings could be attained by using prealbumin level as a screening measure for malnutrition. With a cost of the prealbumin lab test being between \$20.38-27.52, drawing a level four times during an average length of stay (52.4 days) would cost \$81.52-110.08 per patient screened. Prostat 64 costs approximately \$20 per bottle; there are 30 doses in one bottle, which factors a cost per dose at approximately \$0.66. At a cost of \$2.64 for a QID dosing per patient per day with an average length of stay at 52.4 days, the average cost per patient treatment would be \$138.34. The financial implications alone could make a compelling argument for this screening method and protocol guideline. The major limitation of this analysis is that it depends on projected savings from a hypothetical increase in cost from readmission to the hospital, length of stay, and complications from secondary infections such as pneumonia and urinary tract infections. While the benefits of identifying and treating malnutrition are well documented, few studies have actually evaluated the cost analysis caused by the implications of malnutrition (Potter & Luxton, 1999).

In conclusion, malnutrition is a problem in the skilled nursing facility. This project found a positive effect of an oral enriched protein supplement protocol guideline on prealbumin levels in malnourished skilled nursing facility patients. It demonstrated that using a prealbumin level for the identification of patients with malnutrition newly admitted to a skilled nursing facility is a cost effective, accurate tool for malnutrition screening. Future prospective research is necessary to further validate the findings of this

project and show a cost benefit of using a prealbumin level and an oral protein supplement for screening and treatment of malnutrition.

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